

MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM FOR MODELLING EVAPOTRANSPIRATION TIME SERIES

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Abstract: *The evapotranspiration has a significant role in understanding and forecasting climate. Since it depends on many factors, considering and including all these factors represent a challenging task for many researchers. This study introduces a model for predicting the evapotranspiration values for the next month. The model is based on a composition of four artificial neural networks. The networks differ in the input vectors, hidden layers and activation functions. Also they have different structure, while some are recurrent networks, the others are feed-forward. The design of these networks is governed by understanding the statistical properties of the data considered. Different features of the input layer demand different network design. We investigate the effects of each additional network in developing this system. The results are discussed on real data sets. The data sets contain monthly observations from January 1980 to December 2010 of temperature, vapor pressure, wind speed, humidity, sunshine hours and estimated evapotranspiration for the current month. The evapotranspiration values comprise the time series of monthly values that we want to model, aiming to forecast values for the one month ahead. We discuss how the model's efficiency improves by including each additional network into the system and compare the results in terms of the root mean square error, the mean absolute error and the correlation with the real data.*

Keywords: *Neural networks, evapotranspiration, time series.*